
PROXIMATE, FUNCTIONAL AND SENSORY EVALUATION OF PEANUT COATED WITH RICE- AVOCADO SEED FLOUR COMPOSITES

Dr Ochulor Deborah.O., Ejelonu Nelson. C and Decency Favour.C

Department of Food Science and Technology.

Federal Polytechnic Nekede. Owerri

Email- ejelonunelson@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This work is concerned with the enrichment of peanuts by the addition of two plants that is, avocado seed (*Persea Americana*) and rice grains (*Oryza sativa*) into the coating of the peanuts. These two underutilized seeds were processed (cleaned, sliced, washed, sun-dried, milled, cooled, sieved and packaged) into fine flour and incorporated into the peanut with other ingredients. The proximate compositions, functional compositions and sensorial acceptability of the peanut coated with rice-avocado seed composite flour were determined. The proximate composition showed that moisture content ranged from 8.34 – 9.86%, dry matter content ranged from 90.15% – 91.67%, ash content ranged from 1.88% - 2.36%, crude protein content ranged from 11.75% - 14.78%, crude fiber content ranged from 0.78% - 0.91%, crude fat content ranged from 19.78% - 24.67% carbohydrate content ranged from 48.944% - 55.44%. the functional composition showed that foam capacity ranged from 25.00% - 30.00%, tapped density ranged from 0.733g/ml – 0.770g/ml, loose density ranged from 0.599g/ml – 0.628g/ml, water absorption capacity ranged from 3.34g/g – 3.78g/g, oil absorption capacity ranged from 2.52g/g – 2.78g/g, gelation capacity ranged from 16.25%w/v – 18.93%w/v, gelatinization temperature ranged from 85.00°C – 105.00°C, emulsification capacity ranged from 59.09% - 62.78%. However, the sensory evaluation revealed that all the samples had no significant difference in taste, colour, aroma, texture and general acceptability. Sample DFC and FDC (100% rice flour and 95% - 5% avocado seed flour) was preferred over other samples. The research work would firmly support the healthy consumption of peanut

and also enhancing the production of peanut coated with healthy benefiting seeds (rice-avocado seed flours). This research would also provide an insight on diverse peanut delicacies with high level of fortification.

INTRODUCTION

Peanuts or “groundnuts” as they are known in some parts of the world are the edible seeds of a legume. Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is technically considered as pea and belongs to the family (fabaceae) of bean/legume. Although a legume; it is generally included amongst the oilseeds due to its high oil content. Peanuts are rich in protein, oil and fibres. Apart from oil, peanuts are widely used for production of peanut butter, confections, roasted peanuts, snack products, extenders in meat product formulation, soups and desserts. (Suchoszek-Lukaniuk *et al.*, 2011). Avocado (*Persea americana*) belongs to the Lauraceae family of tropical and Mediterranean trees and shrubs. It has been a popular food, for treatment of skin eruptions and medicinal purposes due to its high nutrition content as well as for its therapeutic properties. (Shruti and Padma, 2015). Avocado is considered the world’s healthiest fruit, because of its nutrient contents such as vitamin K, dietary fiber, potassium, folic acid, vitamin B6, copper and reasonable calories. In Philippines, two distinct types of avocado exist, namely the green-fruited and the purple fruited types. Avocados are harvested with hand-held poles and baskets. Fruits are picked when mature but still hard. The fruits do not mature same time, so selective harvesting is usually practiced. (Rachel, 2012). Avocado seed, which is typically discarded as waste is also a rich source of nutrients. The avocado seed or pit, is the storage organ of the plant and contains a wealth of important nutrients.

Rice is the seed of the grass specie *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice) or *Oryza glaberrima* (African rice). As a cereal grain, it is the most widely consumed staple food for a large part of the world’s human population especially in Asia. Rice provides 20% of the world’s dietary energy supply, while wheat supplies 19% and maize 50% (FAO, 2004). Rice is consumed by the rich and poor as well as rural and urban households.

Rice is a part of the balanced diet along with vegetables, pulses, eggs, meat and fruits. In general, it is recommended to store rice in the form of paddy rather than as milled rice, since the husk provides protection against insects and helps prevent quality deterioration.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Production of Coated Peanut: Fresh peanut was selected, washed, blanched, air dried at room temperature (27°C) for 24hours. The flour (composite flour of rice-avocado seed) was mixed together with baking powder, nutmeg powder and salt and set aside. Eggs were beaten together with sugar in another bowl. A little of the egg mixture was poured over the peanuts. The bowl was shaken until mixture coats all the peanuts. Some of the flour mixture was sprinkled over the peanut and shaken until peanuts are completely coated with flour. Oil is heated on medium and fried in batches until golden brown. It was allowed to cool completely and packaged in an airtight container.

Fig 1 Flow chart showing peanut production

SAMPLE FORMULATION

SAMPLE	RICE FLOUR%	AVOCADO SEED FLOUR %
DCF	100	-
FDC	95	5
CFD	90	10
CDF	85	15

DCF - Peanut coated with 100% Rice flour

FDC - Peanut coated with 95% Rice flour and 5% Avocado flour

CFD - Peanut coated with 90% Rice flour and 10% Avocado flour

CDF - Peanut coated with 85% Rice flour and 15% Avocado flour

METHODS

The proximate Analysis was determined using the standard methods as described by (FAO, 2012). Functional analysis were carried by method stipulated by (AOAC, 2011) while the hedonic scale was used to evaluate the sensory characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Proximate properties of peanut snacks coated with rice – avocado seed composite flour

Properties/ samples(%)	DCF	FDC	CFD	CDF
Moisture content	9.44±0.02	8.63±0.04	8.34±0.02	9.86±0.02
Dry matter	90.57±0.02	91.37±0.04	91.67±0.02	90.15±0.02
Ash content	2.18±0.03	2.36±0.02	1.93±0.01	1.88±0.03
Protein	11.75±0.01	13.88±0.03	14.78±0.04	13.88±0.03
Fat	20.35±0.40	19.78±0.02	23.63±0.04	24.67±0.04
Fibre content	0.85±0.01	0.91±0.01	0.88±0.01	0.78±0.03
Carbohydrate	55.44±0.30	54.45±0.14	50.46±0.06	48.94±0.09

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 2 Functional properties of peanut snacks coated with rice – avocado seed composite flour

Properties/ Samples		DFC	FDC	CFD	CDF
Foam Capacity(%)		27.50±4.00	25.00±0.00	27.50±4.00	30.00±0.00
Tapped density (g/ml)	density	0.733±0.003	0.76±0.002	0.770±0.001	0.759±0.006
Loose Density (g/ml)	Density	0.607±0.01	0.628±0.02	0.618±0.00	0.599±0.002
Emulsification (%)	cap	62.73±0.00	60.42±0.00	59.09±0.00	61.82±0.00
Gelation (%w/v)	cap	16.25±0.06	18.95±0.08	18.53±0.50	16.67±0.00
Gelation (°C)	Temp	85.00±0.00	96.00±1.00	102.50±4.00	105.00±0.00
WAC (g/g)		3.34±0.02	3.62±0.01	3.45±0.00	3.78±0.00
OAC(g/g)		2.58±0.03	2.78±0.01	2.77±0.01	2.52±0.05

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 3 Sensory properties of peanut snacks coated with rice – avocado seed composite flour

Properties/ samples(%)	DFC	FDC	CFD	CDF	LSD
Taste	7.60 ^a	7.20 ^a	6.10 ^a	6.50 ^a	1.50
Colour	7.00 ^a	7.70 ^c	6.40 ^{ab}	6.30 ^c	0.67
Aroma	6.70 ^a	7.60 ^a	6.00 ^{ab}	5.90 ^{ab}	1.08
Texture	6.70 ^{ab}	7.10 ^b	6.30 ^b	6.50 ^b	1.60
General acceptability	7.70 ^a	7.40 ^a	6.70 ^a	5.60 ^{ab}	1.71

The proximate composition obtained from the peanut coated with rice-avocado seed flour composites blends is presented in table 1. The moisture content in food can have a significant impact on factors such as the product taste, texture, appearance, shape and weight. It has implications on legal and labeling requirement. Economically important requirements, the shelf life of the products, food quality measurement and food processing operations. The moisture content of

the samples are DFC 9.44%, FDC 8.63% CFD 8.34%, CDF 9.86%. Sample CFD had the lowest 8.34% while sample CDF 9.86% had the highest moisture content of 9.86% which is not in agreement with evaluation of peanut with wheat flour carried out by (Maitera, 2014). Dry matter content is the amount of dried sample that after all the moisture content is removed from the sample i.e. the sample with high moisture content have lower dry matter. This indicates that the product which had low moisture content have longer shelf life. Whereas the peanut containing higher moisture is sensitive to mold formation (Adeyemi, et al, 2002). The dry matter content ranged from 9.015 ± 0.02 to 91.67 ± 0.02 . The dry matters were generally high and this is in alignment with that (87.59 ± 94.51) obtained by James 2000 for peanut carried out with wheat flour. Ash content is important for several reasons. It is a part of proximate analysis for nutritional evaluation. Ash is a non-organic compound containing mineral content of food, and nutritionally with aids in the metabolism of other organic compounds such as fat and carbohydrates (Noorul et al., 2016). The ash contents as shown in the table varies from 1.88 ± 0.03 – 2.36 ± 0.02 with sample CDF (1.88 ± 0.03) having the lowest mean value and sample FDC (2.36 ± 0.02) had the highest mean value. Protein is a micronutrients.

It is one of three nutrient found in food that the body needs in large amount. It is essential for the maintenance and building of body tissues and muscles. The protein content is significantly different and varies from 11.75 ± 0.01 – 14.78 ± 0.04 with sample DFC (11.75 ± 0.01) having the least mean value while CFD (14.78 ± 0.04) had the greatest mean value. These results are not in agreement with those found in previous studies carried out on peanut which has 25.02% to 36.14% (Ocheme et al, 2018). Crude fibre (CF) is the residue of plant food left after extraction by dilute acid followed by dilute alkali. The increase in fibre was observed as an improvement in the nutrients status, since they are agent in food which aids in adsorption during digestion process, decreasing your chance of constipation (Ubhor et al, 2022). The fibre content of the coated peanut as seen in the table ranges from CDF (0.78 ± 0.03) – FDC (0.91 ± 0.01). This is in agreement with previous

work carried out on peanut coated with wheat, which had 0.08% - 0.12% (Reena and Anuchudar, 2018).

Fat refers to a type of macronutrients that provides energy, helps absorb vitamins and maintain healthy cells. Fat plays an important role in determining the shelf life of foods. The relatively low amount of fats present in peanut would enable longer shelf life as a rate of rancidity which could lead to production of off flavors and odors will be reduced drastically. Carbohydrate is one of the three macronutrients which is responsible for supplying energy to the body. The carbohydrate content of the coated peanut ranged from 48.94 ± 0.9) to (55.44 ± 0.30) . the highest increase in carbohydrate contents of the coated peanut in sample DFC (55.44 ± 0.30) could be due to increase in proportion of the rice in the flour blends, however, the carbohydrates content were generally high compared favourably with the 49.60% - 56.40% reported by (Ijaetmas, 2012) on peanut coated with wheat flour. The results obtained from the functional properties of peanut coated with rice-avocado seed flour composite blends are shown in table 2. Foam capacity (%) represents the ability of the flour proteins to incorporate and retain air, a property associated with the formation of light, porous structures in fired or baked product. According to Kinsella (1981). The foam capacity ranged from 25.0% (FDA) to 30.0% (CDF) FDC 25.0% recorded the lowest value while sample CDF recorded the highest foam capacity. Tapped density (g/ml) the difference between and loose densities provides information about particle packing and flow characteristics. (Rabbani and Ali, 2009)

The Tapped density values ranged from 0.733 ± 0.03 to 0.770 ± 0.0019 g/ml with the DFC 0.733 g/ml having the least and CFD had the highest value 0.770 g/ml. Loose density (g/ml) is the mass of a sample per unit volume, when the sample is poured loosely into a container without compacting or tapping. It measures how much space the flour occupies in its natural, uncompressed state. The loose density varies from 0.599 ± 0.002 to 0.682 ± 0.02 with sample CDF (0.599 ± 0.002) having the highest value. Water absorption capacity (g/g) indicates the ability of the flour to absorb and retain water, reflecting the presence of

hydrophilic constituents such as carbohydrates, fiber and proteins (Aremu et al, 2006). The range varies between 3.34 ± 0.02 to 3.78 ± 0.02 with DFC 3.34g/g having the least and CDF (3.78g/g) having the highest. Oil Absorption Capacity (OAC) (g/g) it reflects the flour's ability to bind lipids, influencing mouthfeel, flavor retention and texture of fried snacks. These values ranged from 2.52g/g (CDF) to 2.78g/g (FDC). Sample FDC showed the highest oil absorption while sample CDF 49 had the lowest value. The findings aligns with Matilsky *et al* (2009) who reported that oil binding capacity increases with the presence of nonpolar amino acids and denatured proteins.

Gelation capacity (% w/v), it refers to the ability of flour or starch to form gel when it is heated in water and the cooled. It indicates how well the flour components can absorb water, swell, and then form a semi-solid or solid gel network upon cooling. It values ranged from 16.25% to 18.93 (FDC). Gelatinization temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) is the temperature at which starch granules in the flour begin to swell and lose their crystalline structure when heated in water. Where the starch-water system thickens and turns into a paste/gel. It ranged from 85°C to 105°C , with DFC (85°C) having the lowest value and CDF (105°C) having the highest value. Emulsification capacity (%), it measures how well the flour can keep on and water mixed together by forming a stable layer around oil droplets and preventing separation. It ranged between 59.09% to 62.73% with CFD (59.09) having the lowest value and DFC (62.73) having the highest value.

Table 3 represents the sensory evaluation of peanut coated with rice – avocado pear seed composite flour Aroma in foods refers to the collection of volatile compounds that give rise to strong pleasant smell of the food. (Bruno, 2001). The study of food aroma is important in understanding the components of food and their impact on consumer perception. The aroma value of coated peanut varies from 5.90 to 7.60 with sample CDF (5.90) having the least while sample FDC (7.60) had the highest value. FDC have the most pleasant aroma due to the rice flour tend to produce mild aroma, while avocado contribute bitter note when used excessively. Taste perceived flavor and palatability of

the coated peanut. These impressions are formed by the chemical sensation of taste and smell. The value of the coated peanut taste was slightly different and varies from 6.10 – 7.60 with sample CFD (6.10) having the least mean while DFC (7.60) had the highest mean value DFC and FD had balanced flavor due to optimal ratio of rice flour and avocado seed flour and CDF have higher avocado seed level giving slightly bitter notes. Colour, visual appeal and evenness of the coating. Is an important sensional attribute that has a direct influences on food selection and acceptability. The colour varies from 6.30 to 7.70 with sample CDF (6.30) having the least value while sample FDC (7.70) had the highest mean value. The poor value of colour in CDF maybe as a result of high proportion of avocado seed flour blends.

Texture; mouthfeel (crispness, crunchness, hardness) refers to the sensation that are experimented inside the mouth while eating or drinking. This can include textures that touch the tongue, root of the mouth, teeth throat or it can refer to an after taste. The value of the coated peanut mouthfeel was slightly different and varies from 6.30 to 7.100 with sample (7.10) having the highest mean value. General acceptability; overall liking a combination of all the parameters. The mean score for the coated peanut general acceptability was significantly different and varies from 5.60 to 7.70 with sample CDF (5.60) having the least mean value. This implies that CDF flour lower acceptability suggests excessive avocado seed flour negatively affected overall sensory quality.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The proximate, functional and sensory of peanut snacks coated with rice-avocado seed composite flour showed that the incorporation of avocado seed flour significantly influenced and enhanced the nutritional composition, physical and sensory quality of the coated peanut without adversely affecting their composition or potential shelf-life. It also indicate that incorporating up to 10% avocado seed flour can improve the nutritional and functional quality of coated peanut snacks without negatively affecting consumer acceptability. Food processors are encouraged to adopt the rice-avocado seed flour

blend to develop healthier, value added snack coatings rich in natural fiber, nutritional and bioactive compounds and promote environmental sustainability.

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